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ENGINEERING PHYSICS LABORATORY WORK DURING LOCKDOWN – HOW AND WHAT?

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ABSTRACT

During the past year, the global COVID-19 pandemic and the lockdowns required educators to redesign their courses for online instruction. Laboratory courses are much more difficult to convert into an online environment or offer for distant learners in comparison with theoretical courses. Typically, there are three different types of approaches for offering laboratory type of work online: virtual laboratories, which are based on simulation programs; remote laboratories, which allow access to physical equipment over the internet; and home-based laboratories, which utilize for example smart phone sensors. This paper presents three different methods for physics laboratory work during (partial) lockdown. The main purpose is to describe how a fast conversion to online access was accomplished within a couple of days with the existing laboratory setups and with minimal additional equipment. The piloted methods were: 1) using teacher as students' hands in the laboratory while students remained at home. 2) Only one student from each pair attended the laboratory and the other one stayed at home. WhatsApp video call was used between the students, the one at home collected the measurement results on a logbook, and the one in the lab worked as "an actuator". 3) Pre-recorded videos were used for presenting the measurement setup and the measurements. After the pilots, students and teachers were also surveyed of their experiences and of their suggestions for improvements. Naturally, the findings of this pilot study can be applied also to offering remote laboratory work in normal conditions, not only during COVID-19 lockdowns.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Engineering curriculum traditionally includes introductory physics laboratories. They are either own, separate courses or the laboratory work is integrated into theory courses. The learning objectives for the laboratory work typically include designing and implementing measurements and reporting their results in technically and scientifically proper way. The laboratory work can also be used to support theory courses. Laboratory work is often designed to deepen the conceptual understanding gathered in physics theory courses. According to Holmes and Wieman undergraduate laboratories that are designed to support theory courses, do not necessary improve students' grades. Instead, laboratory courses that focus on improving students' experimental and intellectual abilities offer great opportunities to learn experimentation, reasoning, and critical thinking skills. [1].

Global COVID-19 pandemic and lockdowns challenge educational institutes especially what comes to laboratory work. It is much more difficult to convert into distance learning mode than traditional lectures. Although, the situation was not completely new. Laboratories for geographically dispersed participants have been implemented either with simulations or remote laboratories for years. [2]. According to a previous study, remote labs can be seen as effective as hands on labs [3].

There are several ways to implement remote labs. Setups for remote labs can be very expensive including robotics that allow students to control real setup online and they may require weeks or months to set up. [4]. On the other end, there may be a possibility to design a laboratory work in a way that students can do the work at home, with the equipment that are easily available [5]. A combination of hands-on labs and individual work at home "Laboratory immersion" was also introduced. It was a combination of hands-on labs with students' individual work at home. [6] Using simulations instead of real equipment may also be a substitute of a lab work, but with simulation, the real phenomena are always available through media and therefore is always only a model of reality.

Due to the COVID-19 lockdowns, there was a need to rapidly change from hands-on laboratories to distance mode in a cost-effective way with easily available tools. Three different solutions to achieve this goal, are discussed in this paper.

2 LABORATORY ACCESS METHODS

Three different solutions to access physics laboratory equipment during the (partial) COVID-19 lockdown were piloted in Tampere University of Applied Sciences. Students from three different classes participated in this pilot and they were naturally informed about the non-conventional laboratory workdays beforehand. Each student participated in one of the pilot methods. To prepare for the labs they also needed to watch instructional videos. Students usually work in pairs on the physics laboratory courses. Now they were either asked to stay totally at home or to choose one person of the pair to stay at home meanwhile the other came to the laboratory, depending

on the piloted method. The piloted methods are listed below and each of them is described in more detail in the chapters to follow:

- A. Using teacher as students' hands in the laboratory while all students remained at home.
- B. Only one student from each pair attended the laboratory and the other one stayed at home.
- C. Pre-recorded videos were used for presenting the measurement setup and the measurements.

2.1 Teacher as students' hands, A

One solution to access laboratory equipment during COVID-19 lockdown was to use teacher as an actuator in the laboratory while the students remained at home. The students were asked to watch an instructional video about the principle of the measurement before the laboratory time. Then during the labs, they were able to instruct the teacher what to do though Zoom video conferencing. From the teacher's perspective, the hard part was to remain silent and not to tell how to proceed in the laboratory work and let the students to have the control of the experiment. There were four student pairs online and any of them could give instructions. If all remained silent, the teacher asked the contribution of each of them in turn. Figure 1 shows this method in action as an example. In this laboratory work IR-radiation is generated with Leslie's cube and the corresponding signal is shown as a thermopile voltage in a multimeter. Teacher joined the Zoom meeting both with a smart phone and a laptop to be able both to stream the video and to follow the happenings in the meeting.

Fig. 1. The setup for streaming the laboratory work to Zoom. The students instructed the teacher in the Zoom meeting about what to do and what to measure. The multimeter readings are visible to distant students.

2.2 One student in the lab, other at home, B

In this method one student comes to the lab normally while his/her pair remains at home. The students were asked to bring their own headsets, preferably Bluetooth, with them so that they can communicate with the distant student. In the lab they were provided with a smart phone stands for easier video streaming. They were able to choose any video call software according to their liking. They needed to communicate with the remote participant in such a way that the principle, equipment, progression of the measurement and the measured values were transferred in a clear enough way. The remote participant was responsible for writing down the measurement logbook.

2.3 Pre-recorded videos, C

Using pre-recorded measurement videos (figure 2.) is an easy but not so engaging way to access the laboratory during lockdown. In this method the same video and the accompanying data is available to all students and thus no variation is expected in the reported results. The students have no influence on how the measurements are accomplished and they inherently don't need to plan or discuss the details of the measurement. Therefore, after watching the measurement video the students are asked to ponder factors affecting accuracy, possible improvements in the method etc. and write their answer in Moodle. This way they are forced to think about measurement related aspects at least to some extent and it also brings some individual variance to the answers. On the other hand, same data for all students makes report checking somewhat easier.

Fig. 2. An example of laboratory measurement video delivered in YouTube and link provided in Moodle <https://youtu.be/LEmeRnqFwaA>. The data was available for downloading in Moodle.

3 SURVEY RESULTS

After the laboratory work, the students were surveyed to collect their experiences and development ideas about the piloted methods. There were 38 answers to the survey and 27 of the answered students participated from home and 11 were present in the lab during the piloting. The instructional pre-lab videos were watched quite well (91% of the students) and the pilot consisted of six different laboratory work assignments.

Figure 3 shows the summary of survey results for all three different methods (A, B and C) concerning students who participated from home. Answer choices were from “1 = Not at all” to “7 = very well”. Answers to question “*How well did you manage to grasp the idea of the measurement?*” are mostly on the better side of the scale and the overall average was 5.2. This divides between different piloted methods as follows:

- Teacher as students’ hands average: 5.6
- One student in the lab, other at home average: 5.0
- Pre-recorded videos average: 5.3

It seems that it was possible to communicate the main idea to remote participants adequately with all piloted methods. The student sample and the differences between method averages are small, and not any strong conclusions about the superiority of any method above the other can be made. However, the “teacher as students’ hands” method seems to have slightly highest average. In this method the student knew that they need to give instructions to the teacher. Possibly, due to teacher’s constant presence, they might have watched the instruction video beforehand more carefully and might have been more alert during the laboratory work.

Fig. 3. Home participants’ answers to survey questions.

Answers to “*How well did the experience simulate that of being in the lab*” got a lower average: 3.7. This is no wonder, since remote participation naturally can’t generate exactly the same feeling as being in the lab. Nevertheless, the answers to question “*How well did you Manage to collect all results and data?*” show that all methods

succeeded well enough in getting the measurement results the average of all answers was 5.4.

Figure 4 represents the summary of answers for those students who were present in the laboratory during the pilots for all three different methods (A, B, and C). Their responses seem to be in line with those of home participants concerning the transfer of the general laboratory work idea: the answer average is 4.7 which is close to that of home participants of the same method, 5.0. The same observation can be made with the transfer of measurement data. Both home participants and laboratory participants agreed that the collection of data and results succeeded well. The averages of the answers were:

- laboratory participants average: 5.8
- home participants: 5.4

Fig. 4. Laboratory participants' answers to survey questions.

Student answers to survey's open-ended question "*Comments and feedback?*" were categorized into positive, neutral, and negative. Below are the corresponding percentages and a few picks from the comments (translated from Finnish).

- Positive 39 %
- Neutral 50 %
- Negative 11 %

"Videos, which show the measurement principle, make it a lot easier to start the measurements. They give a good preconception of what we need to do. Also, the participant at home gets a good view what the laboratory participant needs to do."

“If there was a better way to arrange the video stream from the lab showing what is going on, the task would get easier. This kind of situation requires that the instructions to be clear. For the home participant, it is difficult to help, if there are problems in the measurement.”

“The experience was good. Of course, it is best to learn in the lab, and the connections are not always good. This method requires a lot of own activity from the students.”

4 SUMMARY

Three different methods for physics laboratory work during (partial) lockdown were piloted. A fast conversion to online access was accomplished within a couple of days with the existing laboratory setups and with minimal additional equipment. The piloted methods were: 1) using teacher as students' hands in the laboratory while students remained at home. 2) Only one student from each pair attended the laboratory and the other one stayed at home. Student in the lab worked as “an actuator” and the one at home recorded the measurement data. 3) Pre-recorded videos were used for presenting the measurement setup and the measurement results and data. It was possible to communicate the main idea of the measurements to remote participants adequately with all piloted methods. Both home participants and laboratory participants agreed that the collection of data and results succeeded rather well in all methods. Student comments of the piloted methods were mostly positive or neutral and only 11% of the answers to survey were negative. Naturally, the findings of this pilot study can be applied also to offering remote laboratory work in normal conditions, not only during COVID-19 lockdowns.

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